

1 Cover Letter

2 **Modeling Reactive Multi-Component Multi-Phase Flow for Geological Carbon Sequestration**
3 **(GCS) with Matlab**

4 Yufei Wang, Daniel Fernández-García, Maarten W. Saaltink

5 Dear Editors-in-Chief,

6
7 Please find the enclosed manuscript "Modeling Reactive Multi-Component Multi-Phase Flow for Geological Carbon
8 Sequestration (GCS) with Matlab", which we are submitting for exclusive consideration for publication in Computers
9 & Geosciences. We confirm that the submission follows all the requirements and includes all the items of the submis-
10 sion checklist.

11
12 The manuscript presents a reactive multi-component three-phase flow model for Geological Carbon Sequestration
13 (GCS), an efficient approach to reduce carbon emissions. This model is implemented in MRST, an open-source Matlab®-
14 based platform. This model has two main features. Firstly, it considers the chemical reaction among the gas phase, the
15 brine phase and the formation rock. Secondly, the independent variables are split into independent transport variables
16 that describe the transport information and independent reaction variables that represent the chemical reaction infor-
17 mation. These independent variables are solved with sequential iteration method. Finally, we give a benchmark test
18 and an application example of this proposed program.

19
20 We provide the source codes in a public repository with details listed in the section "Code availability".

21
22 Thanks for your consideration.

23
24 Sincerely,

25
26 Yufei Wang, Daniel Fernández-García and Maarten W. Saaltink
27 Corresponding author Yufei Wang through emai: yufei.wang@upc.edu
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29 **Highlights**

30 **Modeling Reactive Multi-Component Multi-Phase Flow for Geological Carbon Sequestration**
31 **(GCS) with Matlab**

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- 33 • We offer a numerical program for simulating geological carbon sequestration;
- 34 • The program accounts for the chemical reaction among gas, liquid and rock phases;
- 35 • The chemical reaction is solved with mass action law;
- 36 • The program solves the mass transport and the chemical reaction with sequential iteration method.

Modeling Reactive Multi-Component Multi-Phase Flow for Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS) with Matlab

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ABSTRACT

We present a reactive multi-component three-phase flow program for simulating Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS), an approach that reduces carbon emissions by storing CO_2 in deep subsurface formations. The program, called MRST_CO2, is implemented in the library Matlab Reservoir Simulation Toolbox (MRST) and has two main features. Firstly, this program takes into account the flow or mass balance equations of gas, liquid and formation rock phases, which affects the transport process by giving rise to mass exchanges among phases. Secondly, the independent variables are split into independent transport variables that describe the transport information and independent reaction variables that represent the chemical reaction information. These independent variables are solved with sequential iteration method. Finally, we give a benchmark test and an application example of this proposed program.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yufei Wang: Modelling, writing and coding. **Daniel Fernández-García:** Modelling, writing and supervising. **Maarten W. Saaltink:** Modelling, writing and supervising.

1. Introduction

In many fields of geological engineering, numerical modelling is an important tool for understanding geological processes, analysis of laboratory and field experiments and predicting future scenarios. An example of such a field is Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS), which aims to mitigate carbon emissions by storing CO_2 in deep formations (Juanes et al., 2006; Xu et al., 2006; EU GeoCapacity, 2009; Vilarrasa et al., 2010a; Nordbotten and Celia, 2011; U.S. Department of Energy, 2012; Tutolo et al., 2015a; Lei et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2019). Modeling GCS is particularly challenging because it implies the interaction of brine and a CO_2 -rich phase with chemical reactions, mass transport, heat transfer and mechanical rock deformations (Gaus et al., 2008). Moreover, it requires the numerical solution of a large number of coupled partial differential equations and equations of state that are highly nonlinear.

Many open-source and commercial codes have been developed for simulating GCS. Popular numerical codes that can be applied to GCS are TOUGH (Pruess et al., 1999; Xu et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2011), GPRS (Cao, 2002; Jiang, 2008), CODEBRIGHT (Olivella et al., 1994, 1996), RETRASO (Saaltink et al., 2004, 2013), NUFT

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76 (Johnson et al., 2005; Morris et al., 2011; Hao et al., 2012), FEHM (Robinson et al., 2000), IPARS (Wheeler et al.,
77 2007) and DUNE (Flemisch et al., 2011; Neumann et al., 2013). These codes have been used to assess the efficiencies
78 of different trapping mechanisms (i.e., hydrodynamic, capillary, dissolution and mineral trappings) during GCS (e.g.,
79 Elenius et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2011; Gasda et al., 2012; Martinez and Hesse, 2016). Each code may have its own
80 limitations and advantages. For instance, CODEBRIGHT is good at solving the mechanics but it currently does not
81 include a sophisticated module for the chemical reaction. TOUGH has an advanced module for chemical reaction but
82 it has to be coupled to other codes when rock deformation is to be modeled (e.g. Kim et al., 2015).

83 All the above-mentioned codes are written in classical programming languages such as Fortran and C++ and may
84 include graphical user interfaces to ease input and output. The disadvantage of this kind of programming is that the
85 resulting code is rather static and may be limited to some specific types of applications. It is difficult to extend these
86 codes with new features or processes that were not conceived during the initial stage of development. Although this
87 can be improved by object-oriented programming (Rouson et al., 2011), we feel that too often modelling is limited by
88 the capabilities of a particular code. An alternative to the use of classical programming languages is Matlab, a general
89 numerical computing language. The advantage of using Matlab is that it is easy to add new features and processes.
90 Moreover, it can make use of various toolboxes. One of them is MRST (Matlab Reservoir Simulation Toolbox), a
91 finite-volume based method, which has been successfully employed to simulate various subsurface multiphase flow
92 processes, such as heat transport, oil recovery and NAPL removal (e.g. Lie et al., 2012; Lie, 2019; Parvin et al., 2020;
93 Wang et al., 2022).

94 The objective of this paper is to present a reactive multi-component three-phase flow code for geological carbon
95 sequestration that uses Matlab-based MRST. The structure of the paper represents the necessary stages in code de-
96 velopment. First, the conceptual model for general reactive multi-component three-phase flow and corresponding
97 mathematical equations are given in Section 2. The numerical solution of these equations is described in Section 3.
98 Section 4 illustrates this model by means of a specific reactive transport system. The implementation of the numerical
99 method into MRST is presented in Section 5. Section 6 gives benchmark tests of the numerical code and performs
100 sensitive analyses. Section 7 presents a simple application of this code. Finally, Section 8 gives some conclusions.

101 **2. General Reactive Multi-Component Three-Phase Flow Conceptual Model**

102 Reactive multi-component three-phase flow requires the formulation of various partial differential equations that
103 represent mass balances of chemical species or components together with other mathematical equations for quantifying
104 chemical reactions, mass fluxes, phase properties and other constitutive laws. For a better comprehension, we first focus
105 on chemical reactions by formulating mass balances without transport processes. Then we add terms for transport
106 processes.

107 2.1. Chemical Reaction Module

108 2.1.1. Chemical System

109 To simulate a geochemical system where many reactions are taking place in a coupled manner, the first step is to
 110 separate the reactions into equilibrium and kinetic reactions (Lasaga, 2014; Langmuir, 1996; Chadwick et al., 2008).
 111 If the half time of a reaction is much smaller than the interested time scale, the reaction can be treated as equilibrium.
 112 If the half time of a reaction is close to the interested time scale, it should be treated as kinetic. We can neglect the
 113 reaction if its time scale is much larger than the interested time scale. This partial equilibrium system, which involves
 114 both equilibrium and kinetic reactions, is constrained by the kinetic reaction rate. We note that treating fast reaction
 115 as kinetic may require small time steps, which is time-consuming and unnecessary. Thus, it is necessary to assume
 116 that fast reactions are at equilibrium, while slow reactions evolve kinetically (Helgeson, 1968; Helgeson et al., 1969;
 117 Lichtner, 1985; Steefel and Lasaga, 1994). Kinetic reactions follow rate laws while equilibrium reactions are controlled
 118 by the mass action law.

If the reaction system is comprised of n_s species involved in both n_K kinetic and n_E equilibrium reactions, the reaction system can be written as (Leal et al., 2013)

$$\mathbf{0} \rightleftharpoons \mathbf{v}\boldsymbol{\beta} \quad (1)$$

with

$$\mathbf{v} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_k \\ \mathbf{v}_e \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

and

$$\mathbf{r} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_k \\ \mathbf{r}_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

119 Here, the $((n_K + n_E) \times n_s)$ -dimensional matrix \mathbf{v} and the n_s -dimensional vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ represent the stoichiometric co-
 120 efficients and the species, respectively; the $(n_K \times n_s)$ -dimensional \mathbf{v}_k [-] and $(n_E \times n_s)$ -dimensional \mathbf{v}_e [-] are the
 121 stoichiometric matrices for kinetic and equilibrium reactions, respectively; and \mathbf{r}_k [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] and \mathbf{r}_e [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] denote
 122 the kinetic and equilibrium reaction rates, respectively. Furthermore, the chemical species ($\boldsymbol{\beta}$) is comprised of inde-
 123 pendent kinetic species ($\boldsymbol{\beta}_k$) and other species. Independent kinetic species are only involved in kinetic reactions, while
 124 other species can be involved in both kinetic and equilibrium reactions. An example of independent kinetic species is
 125 given in Section 4.1.

126 Kinetic and equilibrium reactions are controlled by different mechanisms. Kinetic reactions are governed by an
 127 empirical expression for the reaction rate, while equilibrium reactions are governed by the Mass Action Law (MAL).
 128 We can understand the partial equilibrium system as kinetic reaction evolving slowly, which perturbs the equilibrium
 129 reactions away from their equilibrium state, followed by an instantaneous adjustment to a new equilibrium state. As
 130 a new temporal equilibrium state is reached, the kinetic reaction rate may be changed also. For a closed partial equi-
 131 librium system (i.e., without advection or dispersion), the kinetic reaction rates decrease with time, and finally all the
 132 (equilibrium and kinetic) species reach equilibrium.

133 2.1.2. Governing Chemical Reaction Equations

First, each kinetic reaction corresponds to one independent kinetic species that evolves according to a kinetic rate law. Therefore, for n_K kinetic reactions, we can formulate n_K mass balance of n_K independent kinetic species. If no transport is considered, this is expressed by

$$\frac{d\xi_k^*}{dt} = \mathbf{M}_{mk} \mathbf{v}_{kk}^t \mathbf{r}_k, \quad (4)$$

134 where the vector ξ_k^* [kg] and diagonal matrix \mathbf{M}_{mk} [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$] store the masses and molar masses of the n_K independent
 135 kinetic species, respectively, and \mathbf{v}_{kk} is obtained by extracting the columns corresponding to independent kinetic
 136 species from \mathbf{v}_k . Diagonal matrix \mathbf{M}_{mk} is used to transfer the unit of chemical reaction rate from [$\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] to [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$].
 137 The independent kinetic species are not involved in equilibrium reactions. Here, ξ_k^* is used to distinguish it from ξ_k in
 138 equation (10), which includes transport processes. The calculation of \mathbf{r}_k is given in Appendix B.

Second, all the species should satisfy the n_E equilibrium constraints, given by the mass action law, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{v}_e \ln \mathbf{a} = \ln \mathbf{K}_e, \quad (5)$$

139 where \mathbf{a} stores activities of all species and \mathbf{K}_e stores the equilibrium constants for n_E equilibrium reactions.

Finally, to solve the masses of the n_s species, we still need $(n_s - n_K - n_E)$ more constraints, which are based on mass balances of components. Components are linear combinations of species and are independent of all reactions. Thus, the mass balances of components in a system without transport are given by

$$\mathbf{U}\xi = \mathbf{u}_C = \mathbf{U}\xi_0, \quad (6)$$

140 where ξ [kg] and ξ_0 [kg], respectively, store the temporal and initial mass of all species, \mathbf{u}_C stores the mass of $(n_s -$
 141 $n_K - n_E)$ components, and \mathbf{U} is the $(n_s - n_K - n_E) \times n_s$ -dimensional kernel matrix only dependent on the stoichiometric

142 matrix \mathbf{v} . The calculation of \mathbf{U} is given in Appendix A.

143 2.2. Transport Equations

Before formulating the final governing equations for the mass balances of the components, we first give the mass balance of the β -species in α -fluid-phase and solid phase (Saaltink et al., 2013; Carrera et al., 2022):

$$0 = f_{\alpha}^{\beta} = \frac{\partial(\phi_{\alpha}\rho_{\alpha}X_{\alpha}^{\beta})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{\alpha}X_{\alpha}^{\beta}\mathbf{q}_{\alpha}) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_{\alpha}\mathbf{D}_{\alpha}\rho_{\alpha}\nabla X_{\alpha}^{\beta}) - \mathbf{M}_m(\beta, \beta)\mathbf{v}(:, \beta)^t \mathbf{r}' - Q^{\beta},$$

$$\alpha = l, g, s; \quad (7)$$

144 where, subscripts $\alpha = l, g, s$ denote liquid, gas and solid phases, respectively; $\phi_l = \phi S_l$ and $\phi_g = \phi S_g$ [-] are the
 145 volumetric fractions of liquid and gaseous phases, respectively, with ϕ [-] and S [-] representing the porosity and
 146 saturation, respectively; $\phi_s = 1 - \phi$ [-] is the volumetric fraction of solid phase; ρ [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$] represents the density;
 147 X_{α}^{β} [-] represents the mass fraction of species β in phase α ; t [s] is time; \mathbf{q} [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the Darcy discharge; \mathbf{D} [$\text{m}^2 \cdot$
 148 s^{-1}] is the dispersion tensor; \mathbf{M}_m [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$] is the diagonal matrix with the (β, β) entry storing the molar mass of the
 149 β -species; $\mathbf{v}(:, \beta)^t$ denotes the transpose of β -th column vector of stoichiometric matrix \mathbf{v} ; $\mathbf{r}' (= \mathbf{r}/V_0)$ [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]
 150 is the reaction rate per unit volume, with V_0 [m^3] being the reference volume; and Q^{β} [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the external
 151 source term. For the solid phase, $\mathbf{q}_s = \mathbf{D}_s = 0$.

152 Equation (7) consists of a system of n_s equations, each containing a source term due to (kinetic or equilibrium)
 153 chemical reaction. Obviously, solving this system of governing equations is computationally expensive, because of
 154 the large number of equations and variables, that include the equilibrium reaction rates. Instead of studying the n_s
 155 advection dispersion reaction equations (ADREs) for n_s species, we can simplify our problem to $(n_s - n_E - n_K)$
 156 advection diffusion equations (ADEs) for $(n_s - n_E - n_K)$ components that are independent of reaction rates. The
 157 governing equations for the mass balances of components are obtained by multiplying each term in equation (7) with
 158 kernel matrix \mathbf{U} , i.e.,

$$0 = f_C = \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} \left[\frac{\partial(\phi_{\alpha}\rho_{\alpha}X_{\alpha}^C)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{\alpha}X_{\alpha}^C\mathbf{q}_{\alpha}) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_{\alpha}\mathbf{D}_{\alpha}\rho_{\alpha}\nabla X_{\alpha}^C) \right] - \sum_{\beta=1}^{n_s} (U_{C,\beta}Q^{\beta}), \quad (8)$$

where, the mass fraction of the component is defined as

$$X_{\alpha}^C = \sum_{\beta \in \alpha} U_{C,\beta} X_{\alpha}^{\beta}. \quad (9)$$

In addition, we need n_K transport equations for the n_K independent kinetic species, which are necessary to close

the chemical reaction system as shown in Section 2.1.

$$0 = f_{\alpha}^{\beta_k} = \frac{\partial(\phi_{\alpha}\rho_{\alpha}X_{\alpha}^{\beta_k})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{\alpha}X_{\alpha}^{\beta_k}\mathbf{q}_{\alpha}) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_{\alpha}\mathbf{D}_{\alpha}\rho_{\alpha}\nabla X_{\alpha}^{\beta_k}) - \mathbf{M}_{mk}(\beta_k, \beta_k)\mathbf{v}_{kk}(\cdot, \beta_k)^t \mathbf{r}'_k - Q^{\beta_k}, \quad \alpha = l, g, s; \quad (10)$$

159 where, β_k denotes the independent kinetic species; $\mathbf{r}'_k (= \mathbf{r}_k/V_0)$ [mol·m⁻³·s⁻¹] is the reaction rate per unit volume, with
 160 V_0 [m³] being the reference volume. Note that the transport equation (8) for the component does not contain a source
 161 term for any chemical reactions, because multiplication of kernel matrix \mathbf{U} with equation (7) eliminates both kinetic
 162 and equilibrium reactions (see Appendix A). However, a source term due to kinetic reactions exists in the transport
 163 equation (10) for kinetic species.

164 2.3. Constitutive Equations

To close the transport system we need constitution equations to quantify several properties of the phases and of the porous medium. The constitution equations for the density and viscosity are given in Vilarrasa et al. (2010b). The saturation and the relative permeability are calculated with the model given in Appendix C. For the mobile phases (liquid and gas), the flow rate (\mathbf{q}_{α} , $\alpha = l, g$) is given by the extended Darcy's law

$$\mathbf{q}_{\alpha} = -\frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_{\alpha}}\kappa(\nabla p_{\alpha} - \rho_{\alpha}g\nabla z), \quad (11)$$

where, κ_r [-] is the relative permeability; μ [pa · s] is the viscosity; κ [m²] is the intrinsic permeability; p [pa] is the pressure; z [m] is the depth; and g [m·s⁻²] is the gravitational acceleration. The intrinsic permeability κ changes with porosity according to Közeny-Carman model (Kozeny, 1927; Carman, 1997; Hommel et al., 2018). The traditional Közeny-Carman model is

$$\kappa = \kappa_0 \left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_0} \right)^{\gamma_c} \left(\frac{1 - \phi_0}{1 - \phi} \right)^2, \quad (12)$$

165 where, κ_0 is the initial intrinsic permeability and ϕ_0 is the initial porosity. Normally, γ_c is 3.0. The dispersion tensor
 166 is given by

$$\mathbf{D}_{\alpha} = (D_m + \alpha_T|\mathbf{v}_{\alpha}|) \mathbf{I} + (\alpha_L - \alpha_T) \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\alpha}\mathbf{v}_{\alpha}^t}{|\mathbf{v}_{\alpha}|}, \quad (13)$$

167 where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix, D_m [m²·s⁻¹] is the molecular diffusion coefficient, α_L [m] and α_T [m] are respectively

168 the longitudinal and transverse dispersivities, and $\mathbf{v}_\alpha = \mathbf{q}_\alpha / (\phi S_\alpha)$ (Chen et al., 2006; Saaltink et al., 2013).

169 3. Numerical Solution

170 We have to solve $n_s - n_E$ partial differential equations that represent the transport of $n_s - n_E - n_K$ components plus
 171 n_K kinetic species. We can write these equations as functions of variables that we name independent variables. Several
 172 options can be used for the choice of independent variables. In this work, we choose liquid pressure (p_l), gas pressure
 173 (p_g), porosity (ϕ) and masses of kinetic species (ξ_k) and components (\mathbf{u}_C) as independent variables. Moreover, we
 174 distinguish between the main components of each of the three phases (liquid, gas and solid) and the other components.
 175 In our specific reactive three-phase flow case (see Section 4), the main liquid component is water (indicated with
 176 subscript w), the main gas component is CO_2 (indicated with subscript c) and the main solid component is calcium
 177 (indicated with subscript m). The liquid pressure, gas pressure and porosity are associated to the transport equations
 178 of the main components of three phases are called independent transport variables. In fact, these main components are
 179 similar, though not identical, to the mass balances of the three phases. The other independent variables, i.e., ξ_k and
 180 \mathbf{u}_C , we call independent reaction variables. Hence, we have two groups of independent variables

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} p_l \\ p_g \\ \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

and

$$\mathbf{y} = \left[\xi_k, \mathbf{u}_C \right]^t. \quad (15)$$

181 Here, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} , respectively, store the independent transport and reaction variables for all the field grids.

182 As the independent reaction variables generally have not a large effect on the independent transport variables, the
 183 reactive transport system is solved in three steps. First, the three independent transport variables p_l, p_g, ϕ are solved
 184 based on three selected governing transport equations. Second, the independent reaction variables stored in \mathbf{y} are
 185 then updated based on the flow field updated with those three independent transport variables. Finally, the chemical
 186 reaction are solved cell by cell using the updated independent reaction variables. We first explain the calculation of the
 187 independent transport variables stored in \mathbf{x} in Section 3.1, then show that of the independent reaction variables stored
 188 in \mathbf{y} in Section 3.2, and finally describe the solution of the chemical reactions for mass compositions of all species
 189 from the obtained independent reaction variables in Section 3.3.

190 3.1. Solution of Independent Transport Variables

The independent transport variables stored in \mathbf{x} (c.f. expression (14)) are solved from three mass balance equations using Newton-Raphson method for water (w), CO_2 (c) and mineral (m) components; that is,

$$0 = f_t^C = \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} \left[\frac{\partial(\phi_\alpha \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_\alpha \mathbf{D}_\alpha \rho_\alpha \nabla X_\alpha^C) \right] - \sum_{\beta=1}^{n_s} (U_{C,\beta} \mathcal{Q}^\beta), \quad (16)$$

191 where $C = (w, c, m)$. An example definition of these components is given in Section 4.1.

The Newton-Raphson form of equation (16) is given as

$$f_t(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (17)$$

with

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} p_l \\ p_g \\ \phi \end{bmatrix}; \mathbf{f}_t = \begin{bmatrix} f_t^w \\ f_t^c \\ f_t^m \end{bmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

192 Here, f_t^w , f_t^c and f_t^m , respectively, store the f_t^w , f_t^c and f_t^m (c.f. equation (16)) for all the field grids.

The Newton-Raphson solution of \mathbf{x} based on equation (17) is given as

$$\mathbf{J}_t^{i+1,j} [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{i+1,j} = -\mathbf{f}_t^{i+1,j}, \quad (19)$$

where the Jacobian matrix

$$\mathbf{J}_t^{i+1,j} = \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_t}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right]^{i+1,j} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_t^w}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial f_t^w}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial f_t^w}{\partial \phi} \\ \frac{\partial f_t^c}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial f_t^c}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial f_t^c}{\partial \phi} \\ \frac{\partial f_t^m}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial f_t^m}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial f_t^m}{\partial \phi} \end{bmatrix}^{i+1,j}, \quad (20)$$

where, superscripts i and j denote the time step and the iteration number, respectively. The $[\mathbf{x}]^{i+1,j}$ is updated according to

$$[\mathbf{x}]^{i+1,j+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{i+1,j} + [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{i+1,j}, \quad (21)$$

where $[\delta \mathbf{x}]^{i+1,j}$ is obtained by solving

$$\mathbf{J}_t^{i+1,j} [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{i+1,j} = -\mathbf{f}_t^{i+1,j}. \quad (22)$$

193 3.2. Solution of Independent Reaction Variables

194 In the previous section the independent reaction variables are not calculated, in order to reduce the size of the
195 Jacobian matrix. The independent reaction variables are calculated after solving the independent transport variables.
196 Once having solved the independent transport variables, we can obtain the flow field, such as the porosity, liquid
197 saturation, discharge rate, and so on. In virtue of the flow field, the independent reaction variables (\mathbf{y}) are solved by
198 explicitly solving equations (8) and (10).

Equation (8) is solved as

$$[u_C]^{i+1,j+1} = [u_C]^i - \Delta t^{i+1} \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_\alpha \mathbf{D}_\alpha \rho_\alpha \nabla X_\alpha^C)]^{i+1,j} + \Delta t^{i+1} \sum_{\beta=1}^{n_s} [U_{C,\beta} Q^\beta]^{i+1,j}. \quad (23)$$

Unlike equation (8), which has no chemical reaction term, equation (10) is solved with operator splitting. Firstly, we only consider the mass transport in the governing equation; that is,

$$[\xi_k^*]^{i+1,j+1} = [\xi_k^*]^i - \Delta t^{i+1} \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^{\beta_k^*,i} \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_\alpha \mathbf{D}_\alpha \rho_\alpha \nabla X_\alpha^{\beta_k^*,i})]^{i+1,j} + \Delta t^{i+1} [Q_k^{\beta_k^*}]^{i+1,j}. \quad (24)$$

Secondly, the source term due to kinetic reaction will be calculated in the chemical reaction step explained in the next section; that is

$$[\xi_k]^{i+1,j+1} = [\xi_k^*]^{i+1,j+1} + \Delta \xi_{che}^{i+1,j+1}, \quad (25)$$

199 where, $\Delta \xi_{che}^{i+1,j+1}$ is the mass change due to chemical reaction, which is obtained when implicitly solving equation (26).

200 The operator splitting moves mass change of the kinetic species due to kinetic reaction from the transport equation
201 to the chemical reaction step. Thus, the kinetic reaction will be calculated simultaneously with the equilibrium reaction
202 in the chemical reaction step. This is different from literature (e.g., Saaltink et al., 1998), where kinetic reactions are
203 solved in the transport equations separated from the equilibrium reactions.

204 3.3. Solution of Chemical Reactions

205 Given the independent reaction variables of the previous section, we calculate the masses of all species (ξ) by
206 solving equations for the mass balances of kinetic species, definition of components and mass action laws (equations
207 4) to (6)) simultaneously

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{d\xi_k^*}{dt} \\ \mathbf{U}\xi \\ \mathbf{v}_e \ln \mathbf{a} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{mk} \mathbf{v}_{kk}^t \mathbf{r}_k \\ \mathbf{u}_C \\ \ln \mathbf{K}_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

Equations (26) are solved by using the Newton-Raphson method. The Newton-Raphson form of the governing equations is

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathbf{f}_r = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d\xi_k^*}{dt} \\ \mathbf{U}\xi \\ \mathbf{v}_e \ln \mathbf{a} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{mk} \mathbf{v}_{kk}^t \mathbf{r}_k \\ \mathbf{u}_C \\ \ln \mathbf{K}_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (27)$$

The Jacobian matrix of this system of equation is

$$\mathbf{J}_r = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_r}{\partial \xi} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{dt} \frac{\partial \xi_k^*}{\partial \xi} - \mathbf{M}_{mk} \mathbf{v}_{kk}^t \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \xi} \\ \mathbf{U} \\ \mathbf{v}_e \frac{\partial \ln \mathbf{a}}{\partial \xi} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

The solution of equation (26) is

$$\xi^{i+1,j+1} = \xi^{i+1,j} + \delta \xi^{i+1,j}, \quad (29)$$

where $\delta \xi^{i+1,j}$ is obtained by solving a set of linear equations

$$\mathbf{J}_r^{i+1,j} \delta \xi^{i+1,j} = -\mathbf{f}_r^{i+1,j}. \quad (30)$$

208 Besides equation (26), the mass of chemical species should also satisfy inequality constraints to ensure that the
 209 non-negative mass of any species; that is, $\xi \geq \mathbf{0}$. There are two ways to cope with these unwelcome negative values.
 210 One method sets the mass in the $(j + 1)$ th iteration to zero if we obtain a negative value in the $(j + 1)$ th iteration (Carrera
 211 et al., 2004), and the other multiplies the value in the j th iteration by a factor of η_s ($\eta_s < 1$) if we get negative values
 212 for the $(j + 1)$ th iteration (Leal et al., 2013).

Finally, a convergence criterion has to be defined. We base convergence on the relative change of the species, given

as

$$\max \left| \frac{\delta_{\xi}^{i+1,j}}{\xi^{i+1,j+1} + 1} \right| < \epsilon_{\xi}, \quad (31)$$

213 where ϵ_{ξ} is the tolerance value for the convergence (Leal et al., 2013).

214 4. Specific Reactive Three-Phase Flow Model for GCS System

215 4.1. Chemical System

In this section we apply the previous method to GCS with three phases, i.e., two fluid phases (gas and liquid) and one solid phase. We assume the gas phase to consist only of $CO_2(g)$, whereas the liquid phase contains multiple aqueous species. The solid phase only contains calcite. The heterogeneous reaction between calcite and brine is considered kinetic, while the other reactions are treated as equilibrium reactions (Steefel and Van Cappellen, 1990; Steefel and Lasaga, 1994). The chemical system is given as

216 In this case, we consider 9 reactive species: H_2O , $CO_2(g)$, $CaCO_3(s)$, H^+ , Ca^{2+} , HCO_3^- , $CO_2(aq)$, CO_3^{2-} and
 217 OH^- . We also add Na^+ and Cl^- to adjust the salinity of the brine. This is necessary because the salinity of brine
 218 can significantly affect the dissolution of CO_2 by changing the ionic strength, as well as change the brine viscosity and
 219 density. Here, we assume that Na^+ and Cl^- are not involved in chemical reactions and their molalities are constant,
 220 so that transport equations for these species are not necessary. The heterogeneous reaction involving solid calcite ($K1$
 221 of equation (32)) is considered kinetic, because the time scale of the reactions could be similar to that of transport. The
 222 time scales of the other reactions are negligible, so that we can assume equilibrium, which decreases the computational
 223 burden (Helgeson, 1968; Helgeson et al., 1969; Langmuir, 1996; Lasaga, 2014; Leal, 2014). This assumption has been
 224 widely used in geological chemical systems (Saaltink et al., 1998, 2001). We note that the geological system (32) could
 225 be modified according to the field data on the fluid and rock compositions (Forster et al., 2006). For instance, we can
 226 add the dissolution/precipitation of magnesite and dolomite to (32), if the field data show the rock-forming mineral
 227 contains high mass fractions of these minerals.

The stoichiometric matrices for the kinetic reaction and equilibrium reactions in the partial equilibrium chemical system (32) are, respectively,

$$\mathbf{v}_k = \begin{matrix} & H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ K1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \quad (33)$$

and

$$\mathbf{v}_e = \begin{matrix} & H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ E1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ E2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ E3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ E4 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{matrix} \quad (34)$$

As explained in Appendix A, the kernel matrix (\mathbf{U}) for the mass components is calculated as

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{matrix} & H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ w & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.44950 & 0.29525 & 0 & 0.30020 & 1.05921 \\ c & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1.09811 & 0.7212 & 1 & 0.73339 & 0 \\ m & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2.49730 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ pH & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.05029 & -0.01652 & 0 & -0.03359 & -0.05925 \end{matrix} \quad (35)$$

228 We can see that the number of species $n_s=9$, the number of kinetic reaction $n_K = 1$, the number of equilibrium
 229 reactions $n_E=4$, and the number of components $n_s - n_K - n_E=4$. We need $n_K=1$ more constraints based on the
 230 independent kinetic species. Both $CaCO_3(s)$ and Ca^{2+} can be selected as the independent kinetic species. Here we
 231 select calcite. Then the independent reaction variables, which are used to solve the chemical reactions, are

$$\mathbf{y} = \left[\xi_k, \mathbf{u}_C \right]^t = \left[\xi_{calcite}, \mathbf{u}_w, \mathbf{u}_c, \mathbf{u}_m, \mathbf{u}_{pH} \right]^t \quad (36)$$

232 The kinetic reaction requires a rate law, for which we use an empirical model explained in Appendix B.

233 4.2. Transport Equations

234 The first three rows of the kernel matrix (\mathbf{U}) of equation (35) refer to the main components. The transport equations
 235 of these components are used to solve the three independent transport variables stored in \mathbf{x} . The transport equations

236 are based on equation (16) and in this specific case becomes

$$0 = f_w = \frac{\partial(\phi S_l \rho_l X_l^w)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (X_l^w \rho_l \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_l \rho_l \mathbf{D}_l \nabla X_l^w) - \sum_{\beta=1}^9 [U_{w,\beta} \mathcal{Q}^\beta], \quad (37)$$

$$0 = f_c = \frac{\partial(\phi S_l \rho_l X_l^c)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\phi S_g \rho_g)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (X_l^c \rho_l \mathbf{q}_l) + \nabla \cdot (\rho_g \mathbf{q}_g) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_l \rho_l \mathbf{D}_l \nabla X_l^c) - \sum_{\beta=1}^9 [U_{c,\beta} \mathcal{Q}^\beta], \quad (38)$$

$$0 = f_m = \frac{\partial(\phi S_l \rho_m X_l^m)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial((1-\phi)\rho_m)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (X_l^m \rho_l \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_l \rho_l \mathbf{D}_l \nabla X_l^m) - \sum_{\beta=1}^9 [U_{m,\beta} \mathcal{Q}^\beta]. \quad (39)$$

237 Here, we have assumed that the gas phase only contains $CO_2(g)$, the solid phase only contains calcite, and we only
 238 inject pure $CO_2(g)$. The independent transport variables are solved based on equations (37) to (39) using the Newton-
 239 Raphson method given in Section 3.1.

240 The transport equation for the kinetic species and all components can be used to calculate the independent reaction
 241 variables stored in \mathbf{y} (c.f. expression (36)). According to equation (23), the values of these independent reaction
 242 variables are explicitly updated as

$$[\xi_{calcite}^*]^{i+1,j+1} = [\xi_{calcite}^*]^i \quad (40)$$

$$[u_w]^{i+1,j+1} = [u_w]^i - \Delta t^{i+1} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_l X_l^w \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_l \mathbf{D}_l \rho_l \nabla X_l^w)]^{i+1,j} + \Delta t^{i+1} \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{w,C} \mathcal{Q}^C]^{i+1,j}, \quad (41)$$

$$[u_c]^{i+1,j+1} = [u_c]^i - \Delta t^{i+1} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_l X_l^c \mathbf{q}_l) + \nabla \cdot (\rho_g \mathbf{q}_g) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_l \mathbf{D}_l \rho_l \nabla X_l^c)]^{i+1,j} + \Delta t^{i+1} \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{c,C} \mathcal{Q}^C]^{i+1,j}, \quad (42)$$

$$[u_m]^{i+1,j+1} = [u_m]^i - \Delta t^{i+1} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_l X_l^m \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_l \mathbf{D}_l \rho_l \nabla X_l^m)]^{i+1,j} + \Delta t^{i+1} \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{m,C} Q^C]^{i+1,j}, \quad (43)$$

$$[u_{pH}]^{i+1,j+1} = [u_{pH}]^i - \Delta t^{i+1} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_l X_l^{pH} \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_l \mathbf{D}_l \rho_l \nabla X_l^{pH})]^{i+1,j} + \Delta t^{i+1} \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{pH,C} Q^C]^{i+1,j}. \quad (44)$$

243 5. Code Design

244 The code is developed based on the Matlab Reservoir Simulation Toolbox (MRST) library, which is specialized
 245 for multiphase flow in porous media (Lie, 2019). The architecture of the code is shown in Figure 1. The simulation is
 246 performed by running the executive file, which is comprised of two sections, the initialization section and the reactive
 247 transport solver, both including five modules. The grid processing module is in charge of the grid topology, which
 248 can be either structural or nonstructural (Lie, 2019). The fluid property module is in charge of fluid properties (e.g.,
 249 relative permeability and retention curve); herein, we employed the Van Genuchten model given in Appendix C. The
 250 well module defines the well position and other well parameters such as the well index and the mass composition of the
 251 injected fluid. Detailed definition of the well can be found in Wang (2022). The boundary module defines the boundary
 252 condition, which can be either closed or open with constant liquid pressure. The reaction module is responsible for
 253 chemical reactions for the chemical system given in Section 4.1.

254 In general the simulation is implemented with seven steps, as shown in Table 1. After Steps 1 to 6, we generate a
 255 numerical task that will be solved with the reactive transport solver in Step 7.

256 6. Benchmark Test and Simple Sensitive Analysis

257 The developed numerical model is verified against the one-dimensional theoretical solution proposed by McWhorter
 258 and Sunada (1990). Besides, a simple sensitivity analysis is done of the kinetic reaction rate parameters.

259 6.1. Description

260 The benchmark consists of a one-dimensional domain shown in Figure 2, and the parameter setting for the system is
 261 listed in Table 2. The left boundary is closed while the right boundary has constant liquid pressure, and zero gradients
 262 of saturation and porosity. An injection well, of which the radius is r_w , is added to the left of the domain, where CO_2
 263 is injected at a rate of $Q_{g,m} = \bar{\rho}_g A / \sqrt{t}$, that is, the injection rate decreases from an initially infinite value to zero;
 264 here, $\bar{\rho}_g$ is the mean gas density, and A depends on the maximum expected gas saturation, S_{g0} , which appears at the
 265 injection point, i.e., $x = 0$ (McWhorter and Sunada, 1990). The initial time step Δt^0 should be as small as possible to

Table 1

Implementation of the reactive transport model through the modules given in Figure 1.

Step 1.	Domain design: set the length scale of the domain, and discretize the domain. In this step, we generate object <code>Grid</code> that stores the topology of the field. In this procedure, the grid processing module is employed.
Step 2.	Rock properties: assign porosity and intrinsic permeability to each grid cell. In this step, we generate object <code>Rock</code> that stores the rock property of each grid cell.
Step 3.	Fluid properties: define the relative permeability and retention curves of the fluid phases. In this step, we generate object <code>Fluid</code> that contains the functions for the relative permeability and retention curves. The fluid properties is defined through fluid property module.
Step 4.	Injection Wells: we generate object <code>Well</code> that contains well information, e.g., injection rate, well index, pierced grids, etc. The well module is in charge of the generation of the injection well.
Step 5.	State variables: we initialize the state variables (e.g., gas/brine pressures, mass fractions, dispersion coefficients, etc.) and store them in object <code>State</code> . In this step, the reaction module is needed to initialize the chemical composition.
Step 6.	Boundaries: we define the boundary condition and store them in object <code>bc</code> . The boundary is added through the boundary module.
Step 7.	Main loop: based on the information given by the aforementioned steps, we update the state variables stored in the object <code>State</code> with reactive transport solver. The reactive transport solver contains the numerical solution given in Section 3.

266 capture the large initial injection rate.

267 The relative permeability and retention curves are given by the van Genuchten model, which is scaled by two
 268 parameters (α_p, m_p) (c.f. Appendix C). The densities (ρ_l, ρ_g) and viscosities (μ_l, μ_g) are calculated with the empirical
 269 models given in Riaño-Vilarrasa (2012). The hydrodynamic dispersion is not included and only the molecular diffusion
 270 (D_m) is considered.

271 We use the geochemical system from Section 4. The calcite dissolution model is given in Appendix B, and the
 272 values for the parameters are listed in Table 3 (Palandri and Kharaka, 2004). The dissolution of calcite is controlled
 273 by acid, neutral and carbonate kinetic mineral mechanisms, of which the rate constants at 25 °C are, respectively,
 274 ($k_{0,1}, k_{0,2}, k_{0,3}$). The activation energies of these three mechanisms are, respectively, (E_1, E_2, E_3). θ_{H^+} is the exponent
 275 for acid kinetic mechanism and θ_{PCO_2} is the exponent for carbonate mechanism. The shape factor for the reactive surface
 276 area is η_V . The effective reactive area per volume of mineral is \mathcal{A}_s . We use different values of \mathcal{A}_s to adjust the kinetic
 277 reaction rate. The infinite value of \mathcal{A}_s means that the dissolution of calcite is treated as equilibrium reaction, while
 278 the zero value of \mathcal{A}_s means that the dissolution of calcite is not considered. The reference value of \mathcal{A}_s is $0.0469 \cdot 10^6$
 279 [m^{-1}] (Vialle et al., 2014). This value generates a very fast reaction rate.

280 Initially, the liquid and gas pressure are uniform with liquid pressure being higher, which means saturation with
 281 brine. The simulation is terminated (at t_s) when the saturation change at the inlet becomes insignificant.

282 Regarding the benchmark test, our numerical model is not identical to the theoretical model of McWhorter and
 283 Sunada (1990). The theoretical model is a simple incompressible two-phase flow model. Slightly different from
 284 the theoretical model, the numerical model considers the reactions among the gas, liquid and rock, as well as the
 285 compressibilities of the fluids. However, the two models are comparable because the main influencing factors-

Table 2

Parameter settings for the flow system.

Parameters	Symbol	Units	Values
Section area	A_f	[m ²]	1
Length	L	[m]	10
Grid discretization	N	[-]	500
Initial permeability	κ^0	[m ²]	1×10^{-11}
Initial porosity	ϕ^0	[-]	0.2
Initial liquid pressure	p_l^i	[bar]	150
Initial gas pressure	p_g^i	[bar]	$145^a (10^b)$
Initial brine/gas saturation	$(S_{l,i}, S_{g,i})$	[-]	(1,0)
Salinity	m_l^S	[mola]	0.5
Temperature	T_c	[°C]	60
Molecular diffusion coefficient	D_m	[m ² ·s ⁻¹]	10^{-9}
Mean brine/gas viscosity	$(\bar{\mu}_l, \bar{\mu}_g)$	[mpa·s]	(1.5,0.045)
Mean brine/gas density	$(\bar{\rho}_l, \bar{\rho}_g)$	[kg·m ⁻³]	(1010,590)
Parameter for Eq. (58)	α_p	[bar ⁻¹]	5
Parameter for Eq. (58)	m_p	[-]	0.8
Well radius	r_w	[m]	0.01
Max expected gas saturation	S_{g0}	[-]	0.101
Initial time step	Δt^0	[s]	10^{-6}
Reference injection rate	A	[kg·s ⁻¹]	0.1012
Total simulation time	t_s	[s]	9839

^a 145 bar is used for the benchmark test;^b 10 bar is used in the simple sensitivity analysis.

286 injection rate, the relative permeability and retention curves- are the same. The discrepancies of density and viscosity
 287 due to the compressibility is very small. In the benchmark test, we also minimize the effect of gaseous CO_2 on the
 288 chemical reaction, by using already quasi CO_2 -saturated brine, i.e., the initial gas pressure ($p_g^i = 145$ bar) is close to
 289 the liquid pressure ($p_l^i = 150$ bar). Therefore, we can use the theoretical solution as a benchmark for the numerical
 290 model. As we will see, the numerical result agrees well with the theoretical one.

291 Regarding the simple sensitivity analysis, we only analyze the effect of kinetic reaction rate. To get an obvious
 292 comparison between different kinetic reaction rates (as will be shown in Figures 4 to 10), we set the initial gas pressure
 293 to a small value of 10 bar. In addition to the reference value of $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ [m⁻¹], we also use smaller values,
 294 $0.0469 \cdot 10^2$ and $0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}$ [m⁻¹], for \mathcal{A}_s , to observe a visual effect of the kinetic reaction rate on the injection
 295 process. We also use $\mathcal{A}_s = 0$ [m⁻¹] to test if the program will give zero change of the porosity when there is no calcite
 296 dissolution.

297 6.2. Results

298 *Benchmark with Theoretical Model by McWhorter and Sunada (1990)*

299 The comparison of the saturation distribution calculated with the theoretical model by McWhorter and Sunada
 300 (1990) and the numerical results is given in Figure 3. In the numerical simulations the initial liquid pressure is 150 bar
 301 and the initial gas pressure (or CO_2 pressure) is 145 bar, which means that the brine has initially a high concentration

Table 3

Parameter settings for kinetic reaction.

Parameter	Value
$\mathcal{A}_s [\text{m}^{-1}]$	$(\text{inf}, 0.0469 \cdot 10^6, 0.0469 \cdot 10^2, 0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}, 0)^a$
$\theta_{H^+}, \theta_{pCO_2}, \eta_V [-]$	1, 1, 2/3
$(E_1, E_2, E_3) [10^3 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}]$	(14.4, 23.5, 35.4)
$(k_{0,1}, k_{0,2}, k_{0,3}) [\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}]$	$(10^{-0.3}, 10^{-5.81}, 10^{-3.48})$

^a different \mathcal{A}_s are used to adjust the reaction rate.

of dissolved CO_2 which prevents a large amount of subsequent CO_2 dissolution. The numerical results are obtained when the reaction rate is zero and infinite, i.e., $\mathcal{A}_s = 0$ and inf. When the reaction rate is zero, we do not consider the calcite dissolution, while when the reaction rate is infinite, the precipitation/dissolution of calcite is at equilibrium. From Figure 3, we can see that the numerical results agree very well with the theoretical solution. Because of the very low dissolution of CO_2 into brine, the results from the numerical simulations are slightly smaller than the theoretical one, but the discrepancy between the numerical and theoretical results is negligible.

Simple Sensitive Analysis on Reaction Rate

We also analyze the effect of the kinetic reaction rate by changing the specific area, \mathcal{A}_s . In the following simulations, the initial gas pressure of the domain is set to 10 [bar], and initially the system is at chemical equilibrium. The reference value of $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6 [\text{m}^{-1}]$ leads to a reaction time scale of around 10^{-3} [s]. This chemical reaction time scale is much smaller than the transport time scale, which means the kinetic reaction is at quasi equilibrium.

The saturation distributions of the gas phase are given in Figure 4, from which we can see that the results for different \mathcal{A}_s are very similar. This means that the dissolution of calcite has little effect on the dissolution of CO_2 .

However, as can be seen from Figure 5, different \mathcal{A}_s can lead to significantly different changes of porosity, i.e., different dissolution of calcite. If we compare the porosity changes in Figure 5, we can find that the results for $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ and $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^2$ are very similar, and both of them are larger than the result for $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}$. This means that the kinetic dissolution of calcite can be treated as equilibrium reaction when $\mathcal{A}_s > 0.0469 \cdot 10^2$. When $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}$, the dissolution of calcite is so slow that we can only observe very small change of porosity, and the change of the porosity decreases with the distance to the injection point because the time of exposure to the $CO_2(g)$ decreases with this distance. In Figure 5, we also show that the porosity change is around 10^{-14} , which is practically zero, when $\mathcal{A}_s = 0$. If we compare Figures 5 and 6, we can see that the permeability change is more sensitive than the porosity change.

From Figure 5, We can also see that the porosity change is very small even for the cases with fast reaction rates. This is because only injecting CO_2 does not change much the saturation index of calcite in brine. To further increase the dissolution of the calcite, we need to inject water without Ca^{2+} . This indicates that the porosity change due to gas

injection cannot be explained with the traditional dissolution model, where acidified brine is continuously injected into the initially brine-saturated domain. The traditional model (as illustrated in the following section) will significantly enhance the dissolution because the injected ‘fresh’ acidified brine does not contain Ca^{2+} .

The results for pH and molality of $CO_2(aq)$ are shown in Figures 7 and 8, from which we can see that the pH is higher for higher kinetic reaction rate (i.e., large \mathcal{A}_s), but the molalities of $CO_2(aq)$ are the same for all cases. This is because the dissolution of CO_2 is a fast equilibrium reaction, which instantly decreases the pH, while the generated H^+ reacts with the calcite at different rates.

The gas pressure, as shown in Figure 9, is closely related to the molality of $CO_2(aq)$ given in Figure 8. The capillary pressure, given in Figure 10, is closely related to the saturation distribution given in Figure 4.

The reaction time scales are 10^{-3} and 10^1 [s] for $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ and $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^2$, respectively, and the maximum transport time step is <60 [s]. This means that in large scale simulations with large time step (e.g. 1 hour) calcite dissolution can be safely treated as an equilibrium reaction. Finally, by observing that the gas saturation in the case with high initial gas pressure (c.f. Figure 3) is much larger than that in the case with low initial gas pressure (c.f. Figure 4), we can conclude that dissolution of CO_2 can strongly affect the GCS process.

7. Simple Application to Analysis of Partial Dissolution

Because in GCS the injected $CO_2(g)$ tends to dissolve the calcite of the rock, it may change porosity and permeability, developing highly permeable channels that affect the CO_2 migration process. This section will illustrate the use of our code to qualitatively analyze the effect of dissolution rate and initial permeability heterogeneity on the development of wormholes. In order to be consistent with the traditional study on calcite dissolution (Hao et al., 2013; Smith et al., 2013), we also inject acidified brine rather than CO_2 gas. As such, in this particular case, we only have rock and brine phases.

7.1. Setup Description

The simulation domain is shown in Figure 11. The initial permeability distribution κ_0 is generated with the Sequential Gaussian Simulation method implemented into the SGSIM code (Journel and Huijbregts, 1976). The natural logarithm heterogeneous permeability field $Y (= \ln \kappa_0)$ follows a correlated random space function, characterized by an anisotropic exponential covariance function with variance of σ_Y^2 , x -direction integral scale l_x^0 , and y -direction integral scale l_y^0 . Different variances are employed to test the effect of the permeability distribution on the partial erosion. Here, we use a small domain, because dissolution can be very heterogeneous at small-scales (Hao et al., 2013). The left boundary has constant brine flux. The injected brine does not contain Ca^{2+} . Five pore volumes are injected with mean Darcian flux of 10^{-5} [m·s⁻¹] during the simulation. The right boundary has constant liquid pressure, p_{lb} , which

Table 4

Parameter settings for the flow system.

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Values
Domain size	(L_x, L_y, L_z)	$[10^{-3}\text{m}]$	(20, 10, 5)
Grid discretization	(N_x, N_y, N_z)	[-]	(40, 20, 1)
Initial geometric mean permeability	κ^0	$[\text{m}^2]$	1×10^{-11}
Correlation length of permeability	(l_x^0, l_y^0)	$[10^{-3}\text{m}]$	(13.3, 5)
Variance of log permeability	$(\sigma_Y^0)^2$	[-]	0.1, 1
Initial porosity	ϕ^0	[-]	0.2
Molecular diffusion coefficient	D_m	$[\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}]$	10^{-9}
Mass fraction of <i>NaCl</i>	m_l^S	[molal]	0.5
Temperature	T_c	[°C]	60
Initial liquid pressure	p_l^i	[bar]	150
Initial gas pressure	p_g^i	[bar]	1
Gas pressure of injected brine	$p_{g,inj}$	[bar]	145
Injection rate	q_{inj}	$[\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}]$	$5 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Total simulation time	T_s	[s]	2000

357 is equal to the initial liquid pressure. The other boundaries are impermeable. Regarding the fluid property, the hydro-
358 dynamic dispersion is not included and only the molecular diffusion (D_m) is considered. The chemical characters are
359 the same as those in Section 6. Here, we also adjust the reaction rate by changing \mathcal{A}_s . In addition to the reference value
360 of $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6 [\text{m}^{-1}]$, we use a smaller value of $0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2} [\text{m}^{-1}]$ for \mathcal{A}_s , to analyse the effect of the kinetic
361 reaction rate on the injection process. Details on parameters are listed in the Table 4.

362 7.2. Results

363 We first discuss the results of the field with moderate heterogeneity, i.e., $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 1$. Figure 13 shows the distribu-
364 tions of the porosity change, the pH, the molality of $\text{CO}_2(aq)$ and of Ca^{2+} in the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 1$; the left column
365 gives results for the case with slow chemical reaction, while the right column gives results for the case with normal
366 chemical reaction. If we compare the results for the porosity changes, we can see that (1) when the reaction rate is
367 slow, the porosity change is relatively high in the region with higher initial permeability (c.f. Figure 12), and (2) when
368 normal reaction rate is employed, the porosity change concentrates at the entrance. This is because of the high reaction
369 rate. The injected acidified brine instantaneously reacts with the calcite, the injected liquid almost instantaneously
370 equilibrates with calcite, and the generated Ca^{2+} decreases the erosion ability of the injected liquid. If we compare
371 the results for the pH value, we can see that pH value in the case with slow reaction rate is slightly lower, because the
372 dissolution of calcite, which consumes H^+ (c.f. equation (32)), is slower. If we compare the results for the molality
373 of $\text{CO}_2(aq)$, we can see negligible difference between the cases with different reaction rates; this means that the dis-
374 solution of calcite has negligible effect on the molality of $\text{CO}_2(aq)$. If we observe the result for the molality of Ca^{2+}
375 ($m_l^{\text{Ca}^{2+}}$) of the case with slow reaction rate, we can see that $m_l^{\text{Ca}^{2+}}$ is lower in the invaded region. This is because the
376 injected brine has no Ca^{2+} and the generation rate of Ca^{2+} is small due to the slow reaction rate. If we observe the

377 result for the molality of Ca^{2+} ($m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$) of the case with normal reaction rate, we can see that $m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$ is higher in the
 378 invaded region. This is because the injected brine instantaneously reacts with the calcite and generates a huge amount
 379 of Ca^{2+} .

380 Figure 14 shows the evolution of the porosity distribution for the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 1$. From Figure 14, we can
 381 see that if the reaction rate is slow, the acidified brine can generate wormholes along the high permeable region (c.f.
 382 Figure 12) (Golfier et al., 2002). If the reaction rate is high, the acidified brine preferentially erodes the calcite at the
 383 inlet. This indicates that, for a given injection rate, the dissolution pattern is affected by the reaction rate.

384 Similarly, we show, in Figures 15 and 16, the results for the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 0.1$. Figure 15 shows the distributions
 385 of porosity change $((\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0)$, pH, molality of $CO_2(aq)$ ($m_l^{CO_2(aq)}$) and of Ca^{2+} ($m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$). From Figures 13 and
 386 15, we can see that the result for the field with small heterogeneity (i.e., $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 0.1$) shows similar distributions of
 387 the $((\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0)$, pH, molality of $CO_2(aq)$ ($m_l^{CO_2(aq)}$) and molality of Ca^{2+} ($m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$), except that the profile is more
 388 uniform in the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 0.1$. The porosity evolution for the slow and normal reaction rates are shown in
 389 Figure 16.

390 If we compare the results for gas injection given in Figure 5 and those for acidified brine injection given in Figures
 391 14 and 16, we can see that (1) the dissolution penetrates more but the total amount is small in the case of gas injection
 392 with normal reaction rate, while (2) the dissolution concentrates at the entrance but the total amount is large in the case
 393 of acidified brine injection with normal reaction rate. Thus we can conclude that the traditional two-phase (i.e., rock
 394 and brine) model cannot represent the three-phase (i.e., rock, brine and gas) case in GCS.

395 8. Conclusions

396 We have developed a numerical code for reactive multi-phase transport system in GCS (Geological Carbon Seques-
 397 tration). The code considers multiphase flow of brine and gas (composed of supercritical CO_2) and various chemical
 398 reactions including dissolution-precipitation of calcite, that can affect porosity and permeability. The numerical solu-
 399 tion is done in three steps. First the pressures of brine and gas and the porosity of all cells are solved simultaneously
 400 from the transport equations of the main components for brine, gas and solid rock, for which the method of Newton-
 401 Raphson is applied. Second, other transport equations are used to calculate concentrations of kinetic species and
 402 components in a straightforward way. Third, the chemical system is solved also using the Newton-Raphson method,
 403 which can be done cell by cell.

404 The code is implemented in Matlab and uses the MRST (Matlab Reservoir Simulation Toolbox) for the discretiza-
 405 tion of the domain by the finite volume method. This permits to obtain a code that is flexible and easily extensible.
 406 Other chemical reactions or fluid properties can be easily changed or added by changing the reaction model or fluid
 407 property module. Also, the assignation of parameter becomes more flexible, as this is done in the code itself. An

408 example, presented in this paper, is the calculation of the initial permeability field by using geostatistical methods.

409 The code is verified by the one-dimensional theoretical solution of McWhorter and Sunada (1990). Moreover,
410 a sensitive analysis of this model shows that (i) the gas dissolution is negligibly affected by rock dissolution, (ii)
411 the fractional porosity increase due to gas injection is only around 10^{-3} at normal reaction rate, and (iii) the calcite
412 dissolution can be treated as equilibrium reaction at reservoir condition.

413 We also applied the numerical code to the simulation of calcite dissolution in two-dimensional heterogeneous fields.
414 Initially the brine has a low gas pressure (i.e., low $CO_2(aq)$ concentration and high pH). Brine saturated with high gas
415 pressure is injected at the left boundary. Results show that (i) calcite dissolves mainly at the inlet when the reaction
416 rate law is fast, (ii) effects on pH and $CO_2(aq)$ are seen further away from the acidified brine injection even if the
417 dissolution only appears at the inlet when the rate law is fast, and (iii) dissolution develops in the region of high initial
418 permeability when a slow rate law is used. The traditional two-phase (i.e., rock and brine) model, in which acidified
419 brine is injected into the formation, cannot represent the three-phase (i.e., rock, brine and gas) case in GCS, in which
420 gaseous CO_2 is injected into the formation. Under reservoir condition, the two-phase model predicts concentrated
421 dissolution at the inlet, whereas the dissolution penetrates more according to the three-phase flow model.

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426 **Code availability section**

427 Name of the code/library: MRST_C02

428 Contact:yufei.wang@upc.edu,daniel.fernandez.g@upc.edu,maarten.saaltink@upc.edu

429 Hardware requirements: normal PC

430 Program language: Matlab

431 Software required: Matlab

432 Program size: 4 Mb

433 The source codes are available for downloading at the link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6956860>

434 A. Kernel Matrix

The mass components (\mathbf{u}), independent on chemical reactions, are stored in $(n_s - n_K - n_E)$ -dimensional vector defined as

$$\mathbf{u}_C = \mathbf{U} \boldsymbol{\xi} = \mathbf{U} \boldsymbol{\xi}_0, \quad (45)$$

that is

$$\frac{d\mathbf{u}_C}{dt} = \mathbf{U} \frac{d\boldsymbol{\xi}}{dt} = \mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{M}_m \times \mathbf{v}^t \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (46)$$

Therefore, the kernel matrix (\mathbf{U}) should satisfy

$$\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{M}_m \times \mathbf{v}^t = \mathbf{0}, \quad (47)$$

435 with diagonal matrix \mathbf{M}_m storing the molar masses of all the species. The method of calculating \mathbf{U} is given in the
436 following.

Let $\mathbf{v}' = \mathbf{v} \mathbf{M}_m^t$, and equation (47) is changed to

$$\mathbf{U} \mathbf{v}'^t = \mathbf{0}. \quad (48)$$

The solution to equation (48) is not unique. A convenient way to construct \mathbf{U} is (Saaltink et al., 1998, 2013)

$$\mathbf{U} = [\mathbf{I} | -\mathbf{v}'_1 (\mathbf{v}'_2)^{-1}], \quad (49)$$

437 where, we have split the stoichiometric matrix into $(n_E + n_K) \times (n_s - n_E - n_K)$ \mathbf{v}'_1 and $(n_E + n_K) \times (n_E + n_K)$ \mathbf{v}'_2 ,
438 i.e., $\mathbf{v}' = [\mathbf{v}'_1 | \mathbf{v}'_2]$.

439 B. Kinetic Reaction Rate

For a given kinetic dissolution/precipitation reaction, the kinetic reaction rate (r_k [mol·s⁻¹]) is given as (Steeffel and Lasaga, 1994; Steefel and Mäher, 2009; Palandri and Kharaka, 2004; Lasaga, 2014; Leal, 2014; Tutolo et al., 2015b)

$$r_k(T_k, p_l, p_g, \boldsymbol{\zeta}) = \mathcal{A}(\boldsymbol{\zeta}) \sum_i \mathcal{K}_i(T_k, p_l, p_g, \boldsymbol{\zeta}), \quad (50)$$

440 where, \mathcal{A} [m²] is the surface area of the mineral, \mathcal{K}_i [mol·m⁻²·s⁻¹] is the i th kinetic mechanism function, p_l and p_g are,
 441 respectively, liquid and gas pressures, and T_k is temperature in Kelvin. Some common kinetic reaction mechanisms
 442 are neutral, acid, base and carbonate, etc (Palandri and Kharaka, 2004). For the case of calcite dissolution there are
 443 three involved kinetic reaction mechanisms: neutral, acid and carbonate.

The surface area, \mathcal{A} , changes as the mineral dissolves or precipitates. The dynamic model for \mathcal{A} is complex even
 in batch reactions. Parkhurst and Appelo (2013) offer a simple dynamic model for surface area of the minerals:

$$\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_0 \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right)^{\eta_V} = \mathcal{A}_s \cdot V_0 \cdot \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right)^{\eta_V}, \quad (51)$$

444 where, \mathcal{A}_0 is the initial surface area of the (solid) mineral species, V_0 [m³] is the initial volume of the mineral species,
 445 and \mathcal{A}_s [m²·m⁻³] is the effective reactive area per volume of minerals. $\eta_V = 2/3$ for spheres and cubes that uniformly
 446 react with liquid phase.

A general empirical rate equation for the i th kinetic mineral mechanism is given as

$$\mathcal{K}_i = \text{sgn}(1 - I_S) |1 - I_S^{\eta_{i,1}}|^{\eta_{i,2}} \eta_{i,c} k_i, \quad (52)$$

where, I_S is the saturation index, given as

$$\ln I_S = \sum_i v_i \ln a_i - \ln K, \quad (53)$$

447 where, a_i and v_i are, respectively, the activity and stoichiometric value of aqueous species involved in the dissolu-
 448 tion/precipitation of the mineral (Sjöberg, 1976; Nancollas and Reddy, 1971), and K is the equilibrium constant for
 449 the interested mineral dissolution/precipitation. The exponents $\eta_{i,1}$ and $\eta_{i,2}$ are usually lacking in literature. Note, the
 450 activity of the solid mineral species is assumed to be unit. Here, we use $\eta_{i,1} = 1$ and $\eta_{i,2} = 1$.

$\eta_{i,c}$ is a function to model the aforementioned kinetic mineral mechanisms, given as

$$\eta_{c,i} = \prod_j a_j^{\theta_j} \prod_k p_k^{\theta_k}, \quad (54)$$

451 where, p_k is the partial pressure of the k -th gaseous species, the exponents θ_j and θ_k are from experiment. Positive
 452 and negative exponents, respectively, indicate catalyst and inhibitor. For example, θ_{H^+} is nonzero for acid kinetic
 453 mechanism, $\theta_{p_{CO_2}}$ is nonzero for carbonate mechanism, and all θ_j and θ_k are zeros for neutral mechanism (Leal,
 454 2014).

The reaction rate constant k_i [$\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] is given as

$$k_i = k_{0,i} \exp \left[-\frac{E_i}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_k} - \frac{1}{298.15} \right) \right], \quad (55)$$

where $k_{0,i}$ is the reaction rate constant at 298.15 K, E_i [$\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$] is the apparent activation energy, and R is universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). (The relation between rate constant and apparent activation energy for the dissolution reaction is given as

$$\ln k = -\frac{E}{RT_k} + \ln \eta_A, \quad (56)$$

455 where η_A is pre-exponential factor. E can be obtained by fitting the data $\ln k$ versus $-1/(RT_k)$, and the slope is E .)

456 For calcite dissolution (Palandri and Kharaka, 2004), the $k_{0,i}$ for acid, neutral and carbonate kinetic mineral mech-
 457 anisms are, respectively, $10^{-0.3}$, $10^{-5.81}$ and $10^{-3.48}$. The activation energies are 14400, 23500 and 35400 $\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for
 458 these three mechanisms, respectively. The exponents for acid (a_{H^+}) and carbonate (p_{CO_2}) kinetic mechanisms are both
 459 1.0. More data on other kinetic reactions can be found in Palandri and Kharaka (2004) and Hellevang et al. (2013). In
 460 some simplified models for GCS process, the detailed information on different reaction mechanisms is not considered.
 461 For instance, results from Smith et al. (2013) suggest that when pH variation is relatively small (e.g., pH ranges from
 462 4 to 6), which is common at the CO_2 storage site (Emberley et al., 2005; Raistrick et al., 2006), the carbonate kinetic
 463 rate can be assumed to be independent of either pH or p_{CO_2} , and the kinetic reaction rate is (Berner and Morse, 1974;
 464 Sjöberg, 1976; Wang et al., 2016)

$$r_k = (1 - I_G) \mathcal{A}_s V \mathcal{K}. \quad (57)$$

465 In Smith et al. (2013), the \mathcal{K} is $10^{-5.38}$ for calcite and $10^{-6.57}$ for dolomite, and the \mathcal{A}_s ranges from 0.65 to 4 [10^6
 466 m^{-1}]. Vialle et al. (2014) use $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469$ [10^6 m^{-1}] and $\mathcal{K} = 10^{-4.21}$ [$\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$].

467 **C. Van Genuchten Model**

Van Genuchten model is employed to describe the capillary pressure and relative permeabilities of liquid brine and gaseous CO_2 -rich phases (McWhorter and Sunada, 1990). The retention curve is given as

$$S_{le}(p_c) = \begin{cases} 1, & p_c < 0 \\ \frac{1}{[1+(\sqrt{\frac{\kappa_g \bar{\phi}}{\kappa_g \bar{\phi}} \alpha_p p_c})^{n_p}]^{m_p}}, & p_c \geq 0. \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

where, $\bar{\phi}$ and κ_g are mean porosity and geometric mean intrinsic permeability, respectively, $m_p = 1 - 1/n_p$, α_p [bar⁻¹] is scaling parameter for the retention curve, and S_{le} [-] is the effective saturation of brine phase. S_{le} is given as

$$S_{le} = \begin{cases} 1, & S_l > 1 - S_{gr}; \\ \frac{S_l - S_{lr}}{1 - S_{lr} - S_{gr}}, & S_{lr} \leq S_l \leq 1 - S_{gr}; \\ 0, & S_l < S_{lr}, \end{cases} \quad (59)$$

468 where, S_{lr} [-] and S_{gr} [-] are the effective saturations of brine and gas phases. The Leverett J-function has been
 469 employed to describe entry pressure as a function of the porosity and permeability of the porous medium (Juanes et al.,
 470 2006; Plug and Bruining, 2007; Krevor et al., 2011, 2015), and thus each grid block has its own retention curve, scaled
 471 from a reference curve for the geometric mean permeability and mean porosity.

The relative permeabilities for liquid brine and gaseous CO_2 -rich phases are, respectively, given as

$$\kappa_{rl} = \kappa_{rlm} \cdot (S_{le})^{\epsilon_p} [1 - (1 - S_{le}^{1/m_p})^{m_p}]^2 \quad (60)$$

and

$$\kappa_{rg} = \kappa_{rgm} \cdot (1 - S_{le})^{\gamma_p} (1 - S_{le}^{1/m_p})^{2m_p}, \quad (61)$$

472 where, κ_{rlm} , κ_{rgm} , ϵ_p , γ_p are the scaling parameters.

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